

Computational Insights about Enantiodiscrimination by Diffusion-NMR

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Enantiomers have attracted significant interest due to their critical roles in pharmaceuticals, agriculture, and food science. The accurate determination of the absolute configuration of each enantiomer remains a major challenge for both experimental and computational methods.[1] Matrix-Assisted DOSY, which employs a chiral resolving agent, has shown potential for distinguishing them in enantiomeric mixtures. However, this approach is often limited by subtle discrimination effects that fall within the measurement error and by a lack of molecular-level insight into chiral recognition mechanisms.[2] Therefore, in this study, we employed a chiral macrocycle (MAC) as a matrix to achieve significant differentiation and propose the absolute configuration of mandelic acid (MA) enantiomer through diffusion-NMR. We also combined these experimental studies with computational simulations (classical molecular dynamics and metadynamics for conformational sampling, alongside DFT refinement) to investigate chiral complexation at the atomistic level and to elucidate the experimental findings. ¹H-DOSY and selective ROESY experiments were conducted in CDCl₃ at 500 and 600 MHz using a mixture of 40 mM of MA and 120 mM of (*R*)-macrocycle (Chirabite-AR). The results demonstrate successful enantiodifferentiation in both frequency and diffusion dimensions. The MA enantiomer exhibiting the greatest shielding effect shares the same chirality as the macrocycle, while the enantiomer with the lower diffusion coefficient, indicating stronger interaction, has opposite chirality. ROESY data suggest that the macrocycle adopts a folded conformation, a structural feature confirmed by our computational studies. The DFT results further confirm that the folded conformation is key to the observed enantiodiscrimination and reveal favorable binding energies for the complex formed with the heterochiral enantiomer, emphasizing the role of stereospecific intermolecular interactions in the chiral recognition process. This integrated approach highlights the feasibility of enantiodiscrimination *via* NMR and underscores the essential contribution of theoretical methods in uncovering the molecular-level mechanisms behind chiral complexation.

Figure: 600 MHz ¹H-DOSY of **A**) an enantiomeric mixture of mandelic acid (MA) and **B**) MA in the presence of the chiral macrocycle (MAC). Low-energy DFT structures of the complexes formed between the macrocycle and **C**) (*R*)-MA and **D**) (*S*)-MA.

1. Cabral, TLG, et al. *Chem. Eur. J.*, 31, 25, e202404694, 2025.
2. Cabral, TLG, et al. *Angew. Chem.*, 137, 5, e202418508, 2025.